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Contributions of Negative Results to Science: Evidence from Journal of Negative Results in BioMedicine

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Abstract: Negative results are generally considered "failure" by the scientific community compared with positive results. However, their scientific contributions are mostly ignored, except for those published in academic journals. In order to explore the scientific contributions of negative results, this study examines the social media popularity, citations, and citation network structure of negative result papers and compares them with their positive counterparts. There are three main findings of this study: (1) negative results have significantly more Posts on social media but fewer Mendeley readers than their positive counterparts; (2) negative results receive significantly fewer citations than positive results; and (3) negative results are not significantly different from positive ones in disrupting science, although their *i*- and *j*-type citations are significantly less.

Keywords: Scientific failure; Negative results; Social media popularity; Citations; Disruption

Introduction

Every fact in science is hard-won, and failures and dead ends are common in scientific exploration (Barwich, 2019). However, the history of science is full of success stories. We can only see failures, dead end, and forgotten ideas in the footnotes. Different from other fields of human practice, scientific failure has an inherent cognitive function. Through scientific failures, we can discover what we do not know yet (Bschir, 2018). Unfortunately, the value of failures seems to be underestimated by the scientific community. The scientific community has developed a culture that favors statistically significant positive outcomes. This culture leads researchers to struggle with positive results and rush to publish them, leaving "failed" attempts behind. Any experimentally based discipline will face the problem of negative results, i.e., the expected or desired effect is not observed.

“Negative results” refer to those non-significant findings (those that support the null hypothesis) (Matosin et al., 2014). Typically, researches with positive results tend to have a greater chance of being published than studies with negative results (Fanelli, 2010). Therefore, negative results are hard to find in most disciplines (Fanelli, 2011), although they play an essential role in avoiding duplication of scientific work, saving public funds, and promoting science communication. However, the publication of negative results faces resistance from scientists, publishers, and market competitiveness (Gumpenberger et al., 2013). It is reassuring that journals such as the *Journal of Negative Results in BioMedicine* began to publish

exclusively negative results to address the publication bias. Publication of negative results needs to be peer-reviewed and, most importantly, reproducible.

Improvements have been made in the publication of negative results. However, related works show that negative results get fewer citations than positive results. Leimu and Koricheva (2005) investigated the correlation between study outcome and citations of articles in the field of ecology and found that supporting a widely accepted hypothesis gets more citations than refuting. Similarly, Fanelli (2012) used papers published from 2000 to 2007 to compare the total citations received by negative results and positive results. The results showed that positive results significantly received more total citations than negative ones in some disciplines, such as applied disciplines.

These studies have three things in common. First, they directly compared negative and positive results, which did not rule out the influence of the author's ability on research quality. Second, papers published in different years have different chances of being cited, so the citation time window should be limited when comparing citations (Wang, 2013). Last but not least, they only explored the citation difference between positive and negative results. The other values of negative results have not been investigated so far, such as the popularity in social media and the contribution to citation networks. In this study, we first match the same corresponding author and the first author's positive result paper for each negative result paper. Then, we explore the differences between negative and positive results in social media popularity, citations, and citation networks, respectively.

Methodology

Journal of Negative Results in BioMedicine is committed to publishing negative or invalid results. We used all the 200 articles published in this journal as samples of negative results. We matched each negative result paper with one or more positive result articles published by the same first author and the same corresponding author to control for author influence on the papers. The measures of the sampled papers are as follows,

- (1) we applied a fixed citation window, i.e., *Three-year citations*, to compare the citation differences between negative and positive results because it was introduced in the field of life science previously (Wang, 2013),
- (2) we searched the number of "*Posts*" and "*Mendeley readers*" to compare the social media popularity differences between positive and negative results, and
- (3) we used the Disruption Index (*D*) to uncover the citation network differences between negative and positive results.
- (4)

D measures to what extent a study has disrupted its predecessors by the structure of its citation network (Wu et al., 2019). Formula (1) provides the method for calculating the disruption index. According to the definition of the Disruption Index, the citing papers of an article (focal paper) and its references can be divided into three categories, (a) only citing the focal paper, (b) citing both the focal paper and its references, and (c) only citing the references. In Formula (1), N_i , N_j , and N_k represent the number of these three kinds of citing papers, respectively. Bornmann and Tekles (2019) argued that *D* is associated with the citation window, so they recommended a citation window of at least three years. Bornmann et al. (2020) suggested using Formula (2) to calculate *D* because large values of N_k lead to small values of *D*. Therefore, we applied Formula (2) with the three-year citation window in this study which is named *D3*.

$$\text{Disruption Index} = \frac{N_i - N_j}{N_i + N_j + N_k} \quad (1)$$

$$Disruption\ Index = \frac{N_i - N_j}{N_i + N_j} \quad (2)$$

Scopus indexes the *Journal of Negative Results in BioMedicine* and provides a unique identifier for each author of the indexed papers. The author's unique identifier allows us to find the exact publication list for each author. The process of matching takes three steps. Firstly, we retrieved article lists of the first and corresponding authors of the negative result papers, using the author's unique identifier. Secondly, we identified the intersection of the publication lists of the corresponding author and the first author. Then negative results in intersections are excluded. Finally, if the unique identifiers of the first author and corresponding author in the intersection are consistent with those of the negative result, the negative result is matched to a positive result. As a result, we obtained 126 negative result papers to 891 positive result papers with the same first authors and corresponding authors according to the above matching criteria.

We collected the number of Posts and Mendeley readers of the negative and positive results through Altermetircs API. There are 310 articles in our dataset with both indicators, including 60 negative result papers and 250 positive result papers.

We established a regression model to compare the citations of negative and positive results, as shown in Formula (3),

$$Y_{s_{kt}} = \beta_1 Negative_result_{s_{kt}} + \phi X'_{s_{kt}} + \omega_k + \delta_t + \varepsilon_{s_{kt}}, \quad (3)$$

where Y is the dependent variable, i.e., the measures of article s written by author k in year t . $Negative_result_{s_{kt}}$ is a dummy variable that indicates whether the article s has negative results (yes=1; no=0). $X'_{s_{kt}}$ represents a series of control variables, including the number of authors, number of references, and the CiteScore of journals. ω_k represents the fixed effect of authors. δ_t indicates the fixed effect of publication year. For the other dependent variables, the models are as follows.

Results

Descriptive statistics of the dataset

Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics of the dependent and independent variables in the regression models. In the collinearity diagnostics, the variance inflation factor (VIF) for all quantitative variables is less than ten, which indicates no concern over multicollinearity.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	<i>Three-year citations</i>	<i>Posts</i>	<i>Mendeley readers</i>	<i>D3</i>	<i>Negative_result</i>	<i>N_Author</i>	<i>N_Reference</i>	<i>CiteScore</i>
Obs	1017	310	310	961	1017	1017	1017	1017
mean	7.981	10.990	59.719	0.118	0.124	5.608	29.851	5.427
std	11.530	44.182	69.739	0.689	0.330	3.266	21.375	5.181
min	0	1	3	-1	0	1	1	0
25%	2	2	22	-0.412	0	3	17	2.500
50%	4	3	40	0	0	5	27	4.200
75%	10	6.750	68	1	0	7	38	6.300
max	161	513	567	1	1	25	199	80.600
VIF					1.160	2.646	2.243	2.053

Regression analysis

Table 2 displays the estimations of the regression models on *Posts*, *Mendeley readers*, *Three-year citations*, and *D3*. We controlled the fixed effects of authors and publication years in all models. In models (1) and (2), the coefficient of *Negative_result* is statistically significant. According to the coefficient value, the number of *Posts* with negative results is significantly higher than those with positive results. In comparison, the number of *Mendeley readers* with negative results is significantly lower than those with positive results. It means that negative result papers are more mentioned in social media but less added to Mendeley than the positive counterpart in the dataset. Model (3) suggests that a negative result paper has 34.5% ($\beta = 0.35 \pm 0.08$, $p=0.000$) citations less than its positive counterparts. According to model (4), the coefficient of *Negative_result* is not statistically significant. However, in Models (5) and (6), the main effects are statistically significant, which indicates that N_{i3} and N_{j3} of negative result papers are significantly smaller than their positive counterparts.

Table 2. Regression results on the *Posts*, *Mendeley readers*, *Three-year citation*, *D3*, N_{i3} , and N_{j3}

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	$\ln(\text{Posts})$	$\ln(\text{Mendeley readers})$	$\ln(\text{Three-year citations} + 1)$	<i>D3</i>	$\ln(N_{i3} + 1)$	$\ln(N_{j3} + 1)$
<i>Negative_result</i>	0.288 **	-0.158 *	-0.345 ***	0.083	-0.239 ***	-0.306 ***
	-0.144	-0.092	-0.085	-0.052	-0.087	-0.083
N_{Author}	-0.041 *	0.000	0.043 ***	-0.003	0.029 **	0.034 **
	-0.023	-0.015	-0.014	-0.008	-0.014	-0.014
$N_{Reference}$	0.007 **	0.012 ***	0.010 ***	0.000	0.006 ***	0.010 ***
	-0.003	-0.002	-0.002	-0.001	-0.002	-0.002
<i>CiteScore</i>	0.017 *	0.000	0.027 ***	0.002	0.024 ***	0.022 ***
	-0.010	-0.006	-0.007	-0.004	-0.008	-0.008
<i>Three-year citations</i>	0.018 ***	0.025 ***		-0.001		
	-0.005	-0.004		-0.002		
<i>Author fix effect</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Publication year fix effect</i>	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Constant	1.344 ***	2.117 ***	2.249 ***	1.136 ***	2.350 ***	-0.458
	-0.397	-0.480	-0.317	-0.215	-0.299	-0.428
Observations	310	310	1017	961	961	961
R²	0.443	0.790	0.506	0.250	0.371	0.502
Adjusted R²	0.222	0.707	0.413	0.103	0.248	0.405

Note: Standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Robustness check

To check the robustness of the results, we first considered whether or not our results are robust over different citation windows. We replaced the *Three-year citations* in the dependent variable with *One-year citations*, *Two-year citations*, *Four-year citations*, and *Five-year citations*, respectively. The results are shown in Models 7-10 in Table 3. Second, we considered different criteria to select positive result papers by limiting the difference in publication year between negative and positive results to five, four, and three years, respectively. The results are shown in Models 11-13. Third, we replaced the $D3$ in Formula (6) with $D3'$, which includes k in the Formula, and further replaced $D3'$ with $D5'$, which switched the three-year citation window to five-year. Hence, N_j5' and N_j5' are also checked in the regression. The results are shown in Models 16-17. All these models suggest that our results in Table 2 are robust.

Table 3. Robustness check

Model (dependent variable)	Negative_result	Standard error	Observations
(7) $\ln(\text{One-year citations}+1)$	-0.297 ^{***}	0.074	1017
(8) $\ln(\text{Two-year citations}+1)$	-0.353 ^{***}	0.083	1017
(9) $\ln(\text{Four-year citations}+1)$	-0.382 ^{***}	0.090	973
(10) $\ln(\text{Five-year citations}+1)$	-0.398 ^{***}	0.098	905
(11) $\ln(\text{Three-year citations}+1)$	-0.432 ^{***}	0.086	687
(12) $\ln(\text{Three-year citations}+1)$	-0.429 ^{***}	0.088	621
(13) $\ln(\text{Three-year citations}+1)$	-0.452 ^{***}	0.089	556
(14) $D3'$	-0.008	0.006	961
(15) $D5'$	-0.008	0.007	861
(16) $\ln(N_j5'+1)$	-0.266 ^{***}	0.098	861
(17) $\ln(N_j5'+1)$	-0.382 ^{***}	0.104	861

Note: *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Discussion

In this study, we explored the contributions of negative result papers to science by comparing their social media popularity, citations, and citation networks with their positive result counterparts. The positive result counterparts were derived by matching negative result papers via fixed first and corresponding authors. Regression results showed, (1) negative results had significantly more Posts on social media but fewer Mendeley readers than their positive counterparts; (2) negative results received significantly fewer citations than positive results; and (3) negative results are not significantly different from positive ones in disrupting science, although their i - and j -type citations are significantly less.

Negative results received fewer citations than positive results partly because of cognitive bias toward negative results by the scientific community (Matosin et al., 2014). Leimu and Koricheva (2005) argued that works that support a widely accepted hypothesis are likely to receive more citations than studies that reject it. A large number of citations received by positive results can make readers believe that nicotine replacement therapy trials are more effective than

they actually are (Etter & Stapleton, 2009). In addition, meta-analyses based on disproportionate positive results may overestimate treatment effects (Fanelli et al., 2017). Nevertheless, negative results are signs "this way is blocked," which stops subsequent scientists from wasting time progressing to the same ways and, hence, receiving fewer citations. Therefore, we should admit the values of negative result journals, which offer researchers the chance to publish negative results and signs "this way is blocked".

Low submissions and low citation rates might be the main reasons why journals with negative results struggle to survive in academia. On the one hand, the time and effort invested in publishing negative results are no less than publishing positive results for scientists, but the citations obtained after publication are 34.5% less than positive results. Therefore, sophisticated scientists would not submit manuscripts until the results are positive. On the other hand, journals with low citation rates are less likely to be indexed by the Web of Science and hence suffer low visibility in terms of recognition (Huang et al., 2017). In these cases, the *Journal of Negative Results in BioMedicine* was founded in 2002 and ceased publication in 2017, with a total of 200 articles published. In addition, *New Negatives in Plant Science* was founded in 2015 and discontinued in 2016, with a total of 10 articles published. The short lives of both journals reveal the survival reality of negative result journals.

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